

Methodologies for Flood Hazard Mapping- A Review

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Abstract

Flood is one of the most critical natural disaster throughout the world which causes a lot of destructions and losses to life and properties. Preventive measures like effective land use planning, flood risk assessment, flood mapping or flood zoning are necessary to mitigate the adverse effects of flood. Assessment of flood by creating a computerized GIS database for the flood prone areas and by hydraulic modelling softwares like HEC-RAS followed by preparation of flood map have proved to be useful. Thereafter flood map is analysed to provide prior warnings for general preparedness and if required for evacuation. Out of different flood risk assessment and mapping techniques studied using some case examples around the world, GIS technique proved to be most appropriate and promising since the results provide good basis for the development of a systematic flood hazard management in the urban areas and successfully can be used for the spatial city development policy.

Key words: Flood hazard Map, GIS, Remote Sensing.

1.0 INTRODUCTION

Among the world's most damaging and destructive natural or geophysical disaster, floods are most frequent and uncertain type [1]. They endanger lives, properties, infrastructures and damage a lot of livelihoods within a short period of time. Table 1. shows top 15 countries affected by flood followed by Fig.1 showing monetary losses incurred in different countries.

Controlling floods are difficult, but minimizing the impact are necessary. It is always difficult to identify which measure is the better strategy and policy to deal with the floods. The combination of the human vulnerability and the physical exposures result in flood hazards. These losses and hazards can be minimised by making aware the public before hand by providing them the reliable and suitable information about flood risks. Prediction, preparedness, prevention, diminishing and damage assessment are the stages of flood disaster management. Flood inundation maps are very helpful for delivering data [2-8].

Fig.1. Top floods in terms of monetary losses [Source:www.worldatlas.com]

Table 1. Top 15 countries affected

Country	Population affected in millions
India	4.84
Bangladesh	3.48
China	3.28
Vietnam	0.93
Pakistan	0.71
Indonesia	0.64
Egypt	0.46
Myanmar	0.39
Afghanistan	0.33
Nigeria	0.29
Brazil	0.27
Thailand	0.25
Congo, Dem. Rep.	0.24
Iraq	0.19
Cambodia	0.19
Rest of the World	4.24

[Source: World Resources Institute 2015; <http://www.hidropolitikakademi.org>]

They reflect for different flood event types, the statistic pattern of a particular site, the sum of people at risk, population anticipation and coping with the disaster and

flood protection works. These have been very crucial for flood insurance rates, municipal planning, ecological studies and emergency action plans [9]. Advancements in Remote Sensing (RS), modelling and Geographic Information Systems (GIS) turned out to be very informative and useful in flood inundation mapping [2]. Floods can be predicted and flood risk areas can be identified via models like hydrologic engineering centres- river analysis system (HEC-RAS) and hydrologic engineering centres –hydrologic modelling system (HEC-HMS) clubbing with GIS and Remote Sensing(RS)[10]. To demonstrate one-dimensional and unsteady-flow simulations of the designed floods, HEC-RAS and GIS are used. Flood maps are prepared for different return periods and these maps are analysed and then compared. This knowledge serves to be helpful in predicting flood. Floods cause less damages and losses in developed countries than developing countries where it is devastating [11]. Successful utilization of GIS and RS have been done in flood disaster management. Case studies around the world are studied and presented in this paper to reflect feasibility and effectiveness of flood hazard mapping methodologies.

2.0 FLOOD MAPPING

Flood hazard maps, displays the expected and extent water depths or levels of a flooded area in three scenarios, which are, low probability scenario or the extreme events, a medium probability scenario with a return period of at least 100 years and a high probability scenario.

These can be presented in either quantitative or qualitative ways [1]. Different methods available for Flood mapping are tabulated in Table 2.

2.1 GIS based methods

The flood risk area in Hat Yai Municipality of the Khlong U-Taphon basin in the southern Thailand, was analysed. Forest resources in the headwater source area of this basin were 42.7% replaced by rubber plantation. Due to this extensive deforestation, the municipality became vulnerable to disasters like floods. They used satellite imagery and GIS to prepare maps for the area .The analysis also revealed that 57.8% of the municipal area has faced high flood risks too. This study of assessment of flood risk helped in identifying desirable risk reduction schemes and measures to prevent any further disasters. It recommended them to adopt some non-structural actions like raising awareness and better forecasting for municipality to improve and strengthen the ability to respond to the flood risks in a better manner. [12]

Geographical Information System (GIS) was used and flood hazard maps were prepared of such areas where available data was insufficient. They performed the study on Gangetic Plain of West Bengal, India. They aimed on cost efficient methods to generate flood maps and their study showed that the regional map showing flood prone sub regional areas. They used the data available in public domain like high resolution imagery to generate digital elevation model. Their study showed an effective way of generating flood hazard maps by completely utilizing the available data of moderate resolution and also by using information from government agencies. [21]

Table 2. Different methods available for Flood by Flood Mapping

Year	Model/Method	Country	Reference
2004	Satellite Imagery	Thailand	[12]
2009	HEC-RAS	Greece	[13]
2009	ERDAS IMAGINE 9.0	India	[14]
2009	HEC-RAS	Thailand	[7]
2010	LATIS	Belgium	[5]
2010	HEC-RAS	Malaysia	[15]
2010	HEC-RAS ,HEC RAS,TIN	Nepal	[16]
2010	HEC RAS	Sri-lanka	[10]
2011	ASTER IMAGERY	Ghana	[8]
2012	ERDAS IMAGINE, Satellite Image	India	[2]
2013	ERDAS IMAGINE 9.2	Nigeria	[17]
2013	OBIA e-Cognition	Pakistan	[18]
2015	HEC-RAS	Turkey	[6]
2015	HEC-RAS	Ethiopia	[9]
2017	HEC-RAS, aerial imagery	Nigeria	[19]
2017	multi-criteria decision analysis (MCDA)	Serbia	[1]
2017	Bayesian network-based model, 1-D steady-state hydraulic model	Europe	[20]

Flood risk maps were prepared, for the GMC (Guwahati Municipal Corporation) Area, Assam. They performed field surveys and contacted various government bodies to know the causes of flood and collected the data required to generate the risk maps. In GIS, geographic data in form of layers such as slope, drainage, roads, buildings etc. were taken as input which helped in creating models for proper management used by planners and administrators. With the help of ArcGIS 7.2.1 and ERDAS IMAGINE 9.0 they integrated the collected data to generate the flood risk map which showed the elevation of the area in terms of flood vulnerability. [14]

Flood hazard maps were generated for Ping River Basin, northern Thailand. They created the hydraulic model of flood prone areas with the help of advanced computer based software like HEC-RAS in RS and GIS. With the help of 1D HEC-RAS flood model they prepared the inundated area and flood depths for flood occurred in 2005 in Chiang Mai province. Then the model was verified by liken the results of model with the RS image and then the flood risk maps were generated by model outputs. [7]

The coastline region, Flanders of north Belgium was mapped. The methods used to minimise the flood casualties by the management in the past leads to increase in possibility of flood in downstream. Instead of preventing the floods the method used emphasised on minimizing the aftermath of flood occurred. By using GIS, they collected various data such as land use information, social and economic data and hydrologic models for the Flemish Region to create a risk based method to quantitatively evaluate the flood risk. The method was implemented in LATIS, a flood assessment tool based in GIS. They concluded that LATIS can be efficient for integrating and managing the data and can enhance the flood risk management. [5]

Flood maps for floodplain was prepared in Lothar Khola having catchment area of 170 km² between two districts, Chitwan and Makawanpur of Nepal. The data was imported from 1-D hydraulic model HEC-RAS, HEC-GeoRAS for preparing maps of different return periods. By using data such as spot elevations and contour in ArcView GIS a Triangulated Irregular Network (TIN) was prepared. He inputted boundary conditions and flood discharge in HEC-RAS for different return periods. The return periods 2, 10, 50, 100 and 200 years had inundated area 230, 239, 246, 249 and 252 km² respectively. The flood caused a potential damage to crops and vegetation and negatively affected the livelihood. [16]

The basin in Sri Lanka of Kalu-Ganga River was studied that receives maximum of south-west monsoon. Frequent floods make the river basin very vulnerable. Two data sets were used for the assessment of the vulnerability of the flood prone basins. Using building data and population data, first assessment was done for every GN division. Secondly, on the vulnerability due to flood of various household in a particular area, a comprehensive survey was conducted. They also used remote sensing, GIS, HEC-RAS and HEC-HMS for flood risk analysis. [10]

Flood prone areas were mapped, of Dikrong river basin of Arunachal Pradesh, India using GIS. Inundation maps for different return periods were developed and compared by maps generated by conventional methods as submitted in Brahmaputra Board Master Plan for Dikrong basin. The results showed that the difference of modelled and reported map inundation areas was below 5% and they matches satisfactorily. They concluded that the GIS techniques are cost effective and successful way of preparing flood inundation maps for hilly basins like Dikrong. [3]

A district level flood hazard map of Ghana was generated. In the study the investigator showed the need for effective methods which are less expensive for the flood prone areas. The prepared flood hazard maps uses various data such as availability of high ground for shelter, number of towns, population density and

area for cultivation in GIS software. He integrated GIS and ASTER imagery combined with Digital Elevation Models and generated maps for study area. The results obtained in the study gives essential data for administrators to analyse flood hazards and create remedial strategies. [8]

Different types of physical and climatic conditions were analyzed of Mongalkote block building good proposal of reducing the flood. It is an immense flood affected area of Burdwan district of the West Bengal, Eastern India, which is affected by two main rivers Ajoy & Kunur River. The data collected like satellite images (Landsat ETM+, TM, LISS-III), geology, climate, SRTM image, groundwater, rainfall data, soil map, flood time photographs, population data, and google earth image were analysed using remote sensing and other software like ERDAS IMAGINE, ArcGIS, PCI Geomatica-9.1. They prepared flood map using Arc GIS-3.2 software. Using this software, a 2 km. buffer zone is formed for both the rivers, Ajoy & Kunur river. Then compared this map with flood map of actual affected area of flood occurred in 2000. They found that GIS is an appropriate technique only some area was varied from actual flood affected area. [2]

Similarly in another research flood hazard maps were prepared, of river Kaduna in Kaduna city, Nigeria by using applications of R.S. and GIS. The river covers large areas in major trading centres of Nigeria. They used high resolution imagery through which they developed a DEM with ArcGIS which then used to identify the flood prone areas near the middle part of river. They created a model of flood accumulation with the help of DEM and further separated them on the basis of their elevation into the high, moderate and low risk zones of equal intervals. Then they overlaid the results on map to generate flood vulnerability map of the study area. They also conducted field survey by interviewing 50 respondents from flood prone areas. They concluded that flood maps can be utilised in the disaster response planning and the flood risk management. [17]

The applications of RS and GIS were described to identify flood shelters and flood zones to provide a simple and effective method which accurately showed flood inundated areas for the Sindh Province, Pakistan with the help of ArcGIS software. They used the OBIA in eCognition software to create inundated maps of the flood events occurred in 2010. The resulted model shown in research indicated the hazard area of 6216 km² while the catastrophic flood occurred inundated a gross area of 7579 km². The difference occurred in mapped and modelled results were insignificant and acceptable. They concluded that the method used is enough to generate flood map shelter sites and hazard zoning maps for flood management. [18]

GIS techniques and HEC-RAS were used to prepare the maps of flood prone areas of the Mert River Basin, Samsun, Turkey. They digitalised the topographical data and generated the Digital Elevation Model with the help of ArcGIS software and HEC-RAS software were used to simulate the flood values of different return periods. Then these two data were integrated to prepare the Flood Risk Maps. They clearly showed influenced area in 2012 flood was approximately 30% with maximum depth reached 6.2 m which caused loss of life and property. [6]

Flood hazard and inundation area mapping for the Awash River Basin, Ethiopia, were studied by researchers where excess of rainfall occurs in short intervals and high discharge of river causing river flooding. This was of a huge concern because of which crop damage and human losses were taking place. They used multi evaluation technique and developed flood inundated zone by combining flood generating factors (slope, elevation, rainfall, drainage etc.). To create the triangular irregular network, mapping of the inundation area was done by processing the digital elevation model followed by HEC-RAS and ARC-GIS to develop flood inundation map and determined inundated area for different return periods. [9]

Another researcher demonstrated the application of HEC-RAS and GIS software used for more accurate results when conducting a flood vulnerability mapping and assessment in Lagos located in the south-western part of Nigeria. They adapted Digital interpretation to perform flood inundation mapping and hydraulic modelling and also collected the data from the study area like aerial imagery of landsat 8 OLI and Digital Terrain Model (DTM). They analysed the data in ArcGIS 10.1 application with HEC-GeoRAS tool extension and HEC-RAS 4.1 software application. They concluded that maps of flood vulnerability is important for Nigeria to control flood disaster. [19]

GIS methodology for multi-criteria was presented for mapping of the flood hazard areas and hazard zones in urban areas. This was demonstrated in Belgrade, Serbia. The methodology was based on multi-criteria decision analysis (MCDA) and GIS. The evaluation considered the severity and nature of observed criteria. It was tested on the basis of three scenarios. First was a new approach to exploit uncertainty applying the analytic hierarchy process (AHP) technique (IR'AHP). Second was the use of fuzzy technique (F'AHP) and the third traditional AHP method (CRISP). The IR'AHP provided the highest compatibility level. The result of the study provided a good base for the development of the flood management in urban areas. [1]

A simple and different approach was considered paper by combining physical and statistical models compared to conventional rainfall runoff model to conduct flood hazard mapping for pan-European River. They used Bayesian network-based model using previous studies to induce return period for European rivers. The simulations were performed by using 1-D steady-state hydraulic model and the results were then generated by using GIS software. The two methods showed similarities regenerating flood zones. Simplified approach showed accuracy too, reduced the computational time. They also showed the aggregated results of the flood hazards occurred in Europe, including future projections and the flood protection standards were considered. The flood hazard area may increase in future (around 35% over a 100 years return period). [20]

2.2 Other methods

Maps of flood inundated areas were generated of Greece and showed differences and similarities in the maps produced for various areas. With the help of HEC-HMS software, investigators simulated hydrologic processes of river basins and for given return periods, hydrographs were prepared. Simulations of the

hydraulics of the open channel flow were performed by HEC-RAS software. These softwares were compatible with ArcGIS, visualization and further data processing can be used for cartographical purposes. They concluded that the flood inundation mapping is important in prioritizing and planning flood protection actions in an initial stage. [13]

River flood risk maps were prepared using the HEC-HMS and HEC-RAS software for the Sungai Kayu Ara River basin situated in western part of Kuala Lumpur in Malaysia. They used hydraulic model results to prepare water depth and flow velocity maps and with the help of these results they generated the river flood hazard maps. The results shown that the amount of rainfall and land used by river basin have influenced the river flood risk maps pattern. [15]

The Dep River Basin of North Central Nigeria was studied and reported that this area flood occurs in different severity every year. These plains affected by flood resulted in the loss of lives, crops, livestock and destruction of infrastructure. In the floodplain, agriculture is the most affected sector with inundation area varying from 68.82 to 146.10 km² for return periods of 2-years to 1000-years. They developed flood inundation map and determined inundated area for different return periods by using software ERDAS IMAGINE 9.2 for remote sensing analysis and ArcGIS 9.3. [4]

3.0 Conclusion

Different literature were reviewed regarding flood hazard mapping of varied places. They used different softwares and models like ArcGIS, MIKE 11, ERDAS, HEC-RAS, and HEC-HMS for the assessment and remote sensing of the same. By using HEC-RAS and ArcGIS, flood inundation of low lying areas that are affected by flood can be determined and mapping of those areas can be easily done. By plotting graphs between different return periods and inundated areas, assessment of inundated area at any return periods is possible. If graph plotted at 0,10,20,30,40,50,60,70, 80, 90, 100 return period and inundated area corresponding to these return periods then inundated area at 40, 74 or other return period can be easily assessed from the graph. It was observed that the GIS technique using HEC-RAS model, proved to be appropriate and suitable method as detailed flood inundation map is obtained. This helps in the prior awareness and in the rescue of the endangered and vulnerable people beforehand in that region. It has been expected for the contribution of an improved understanding of these varied techniques by the scientists of developing countries where limited information is delivered or utilized.

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